

fAsyLex: Accelerating Legal NLP through Comparative Analysis of Multi-GPU Approaches

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I. INTRODUCTION

Natural Language Processing (NLP) has recently seen significant progress driven by new techniques and the availability of vast textual data. Tasks such as text classification have been revolutionized by state-of-the-art NLP models, using transformer-based architectures. However, as NLP models and datasets grow in size, the time taken to train these models becomes a bottleneck in research and application deployment.

While Pretrained Language Models (PLMs) have gained significant attention, many real-world applications have yet to fully leverage their capabilities. Off-the-shelf PLMs often struggle to adapt to specialized domains, posing challenges for downstream tasks that require fine-tuning with specific datasets [1]. This requires additional training steps, making parallel computing crucial for handling the computational demands of language model training. Choosing between single-GPU and multi-GPU training depends on factors like hardware availability, cost, and achievable training speedup, highlighting the need to weigh the trade-offs and benefits to optimize training pipelines.

The primary objective of this work is to evaluate the acceleration of NLP training for the task of text classification on legal documents. The dataset used is *AsyLex*, a dataset of refugee claims from Canada [2]. We aim to compare and contrast the performance of single-GPU and multi-GPU training in terms of both training efficiency and final model quality. We implement *fast AsyLex* (*fAsyLex*) and scale it across up to 64 GPUs. Through systematic experimentation, we seek to address the following research questions: (i) **How does the training time differ between single-GPU and multi-GPU setups for two commonly used PLMs, RoBERTa and DeBERTaV3?** And (ii) **Does the choice of training approach (single-GPU vs. multi-GPU) influence the classification performance on the chosen dataset?**

Our contributions so far are as follows: (1) we offer a detailed and rigorous investigation into the practical implications of employing single-GPU and multi-GPU training approaches for text classification, (2) we compare two commonly used masked language models, RoBERTa and DeBERTa and reduce runtime out-of-the-box by 49% and 37% respectively, and (3) we demonstrate that there is a trade-off in terms of accuracy

TABLE I
PROBLEM SIZES WITH TRAIN AND TEST DATA SET. SIZE IN MEGABYTES

Problem size	Train		Test	
	Size (MB)	Examples	Size (MB)	Examples
Small	2.9	20,186	0.714	5,046
Large	336.3	2,015,096	84.1	503,774

and distributed training. We expect our findings to provide valuable insights regarding the trade-offs associated with each approach in terms of training time and model performance. The code for this work is available at <https://github.com/clairebarale/WHPC>.

II. TASK DESCRIPTION

A. Text classification

The task is a binary text classification task. It consists of predicting whether the decision outcome of a refugee claim was positive (refugee status granted) or negative (the claim was rejected). This task serves various stakeholders. Lawyers and claimants use it to predict case success, identify winning factors, and improve their chances. Judges can analyze decisions for better consistency, and researchers can uncover biases in Refugee Status Determination (RSD) assessments.

B. Dataset: *AsyLex*

We perform this task on the small dataset as described in table I. The dataset includes a total of 25,232 documents case covers (first page of a case document), 6,985 of which are cases with a positive outcome (27.68%). The text of the dataset, which constitutes one input string per case document, is formed by a chain of legal entities that have been extracted from the documents. The following legal entities are extracted from each case cover: *date of the hearing and date of the decision, location of the hearing, tribunal, public/private hearing, in chambers/virtual hearing, and name of the judge*. Entities are concatenated to form one string per document, separating each type of entity with a separation token. An input string example is: “2010 april 28 2010[SEP]toronto ontario[SEP]in chambers[SEP]april 28 2010”.

The large dataset includes legal entities extracted from the main text of the documents. Future work will explore this dataset size.

TABLE II
 TRAINING RUNTIME IN SECONDS, THROUGHPUT IN SAMPLES PER SECOND AND STEPS PER SECONDS FOR THE TWO MODELS *RoBERTa* AND *DeBERTa*
 SCALED ACROSS UP TO 64 NVIDIA TESLA V100 GPUS

GPUs	Train runtime (s)				Throughput (samples/s)				Throughput (steps/s)			
	RoBERTa	vs. 1 GPU	DeBERTa	vs. 1 GPU	RoBERTa	vs. 1 GPU	DeBERTa	vs. 1 GPU	RoBERTa	vs. 1 GPU	DeBERTa	vs. 1 GPU
1	502.92	-	617.68	-	120.41	-	98.04	-	15.06	-	12.26	-
2	395.26	0.79	567.70	0.92	153.21	1.27	106.67	1.09	9.58	0.64	6.67	0.54
4	256.06	0.51	444.30	0.72	236.50	1.96	136.30	1.39	7.39	0.49	4.26	0.64
8	257.49	0.51	429.42	0.70	235.19	1.95	141.02	1.44	7.35	0.49	4.41	1.03
16	256.70	0.51	391.57	0.63	235.91	1.96	154.66	1.58	7.37	0.49	4.83	1.10
32	252.31	0.50	397.31	0.64	240.02	1.99	152.42	1.55	7.50	0.50	4.77	0.99
64	254.89	0.51	386.66	0.63	237.58	1.97	156.62	1.60	7.43	0.49	4.90	1.03

C. Models used

We fine-tune two widely used language models with a masked language modeling objective: RoBERTa, and DeBERTa. Both models have 86 million parameters and are pretrained on 160 GB of text. However, the DeBERTa vocabulary is larger with 128K tokens against 50K for RoBERTa. DeBERTa improves upon RoBERTa in terms of accuracy by using a disentangled attention mechanism.

D. Experimental setup

The models used in this work are fine-tuned on three epochs using Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $1.1e - 05$. The batch size is set to `auto` for the tooling to decide the optimal size at runtime. We use a cluster with per-node configuration of two 20-core Intel Xeon Cascade Lake CPUs running at 2.4 Ghz and four Nvidia Tesla V100-SMX2-16GB GPUs (640 Tensor cores each), 384 GB of memory per node and Infiniband interconnect at 100 Gbit/s. Running across 64 GPUs, we scale our experiments over 16 nodes.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Results on the small problem size are described in Table II. As expected the runtime decreases as we distribute it across more GPUs until it reaches a plateau or slightly decreases again. The best runtime for RoBERTa is achieved with training distributed over 32 GPUs and 64 GPUs for DeBERTa. One hypothesis is that the use of DataParallel (PyTorch feature) introduces communication overhead and slows inter-connectivity between the GPU cards as the number of GPUs increases.

We also observe that RoBERTa is generally faster to fine-tune than DeBERTa, which could be explained by the larger vocabulary stored. However, DeBERTa only slightly outperforms DeBERTa in terms of macro-F1 scores (+ 0.23%) and achieves the exact same best accuracy.

Similarly, the number of samples per second increases with the number of GPUs up to a certain point of stability. The number of training steps per second decreases as the training gets distributed. This may also result from the use of DataParallel, in which the first GPU distributes the work in the form of mini-batches to the rest of the GPUs. As the number of GPUs increases, the rate of steps per second diminishes due to the adoption of a smaller batch size for efficiency.

In terms of NLP evaluation, both PLMs achieve the same best accuracy score of 74.55% on this dataset, both across 8

GPUs. The lowest accuracy achieved is 73.84% for RoBERTa (single GPU) and 73.8% for DeBERTaV3 (32 GPUs), i.e. a variation inferior to one percent, respectively 0.71% and 0.75%. We also evaluate the work on macro-F1 score because of the initial imbalance in classes of the dataset. The best reported macro F1 score is respectively 67.21% (single GPU) and 68.1% (2 GPUs), with DeBERTaV3 performing slightly better. The most significant variation is 6.72% for RoBERTa with the lowest score achieved across 8 GPUs. DeBERTaV3 performance varies less, with a maximum variation of 1.88%, the lowest score occurring on 4 GPUs. We conclude that there is a trade-off between time efficiency, the cost of fine-tuning, and the evaluation metric that needs to be optimized.

It is to be noted that the best runtime setup does not correspond to the best-achieved accuracy. We find that setups with fewer GPUs perform better: the best accuracy scores are obtained with 8 GPUs and the best F1 scores with a single and 2 GPUs respectively, resulting in a necessary trade-off.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We investigate the trade-offs between single-GPU and multi-GPU training for efficient NLP training in the context of text classification. Our reported experiments demonstrate that the decision regarding training setup and its impact on NLP evaluation metrics isn't straightforward. Rather, it requires informed consideration to optimize the balance between factors such as cost, efficiency, training time, and optimized evaluation metrics effectively. Future work will focus on performing a similar study on the larger problem size of the dataset.

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